
BETTER4U Project Management Handbook and Risk Management Plan

**Work Package 1
Deliverable D1.2**

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Executive summary

The present document summarizes the internal management and governance structure and procedures of the project as well as the proposed risk management activities, thus completing the information stated in the project's Grant and Consortium Agreements (GA & CA). The objective of the present document is, therefore, two-fold as to: i) explicitly describe the bodies created within the project, their internal functions and procedures and promote the ensurance of high quality standards by elaborating and sharing on each of their roles and responsibilities, and; ii) to provide in-depth descriptions of the proposed contingency actions to be undertaken when and if necessary, via the partners' cooperative efforts and use of efficient and reliable management tools and methods.

Disclaimer

The present document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including the Annexes associated) and the Consortium Agreement.

Document information

Project Number	101080117
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Statement of originality

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Document information	4
Statement of originality	5
Index of tables.....	7
Abbreviations	8
1. Introduction	9
2. Project Governance Structure.....	9
2.1. Coordination and Management Team (CMT).....	9
2.2. General Assembly (GA)	10
2.3. Steering Committee (SC).....	12
2.4. Dissemination Committee (DC).....	13
2.5. External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB).....	15
2.6. Patient Advisory Board (PAB).....	16
3. Risk Management Plan	16
4. Conclusion	19
5. Contact and Details.....	20

Index of tables

Table 1. Members and functions of the BETTER4U Coordination and Management Team ...10

Table 2. Voting members and functions of the BETTER4U General Assembly (GA)11

Table 3. Members of the BETTER4U Steering Committee (SC)13

Table 4. Members of the BETTER4U Dissemination Committee (DC).....14

Table 5. List of BETTER4U Critical Risks as included in the DoA17

Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
CA	Consortium Agreement
CMT	Coordination and Management Team
CO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEAB	External Expert Advisory Board
GA	Grant Agreement or General Assembly
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
RCT	Randomized Clinical Trial
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

D1.2 BETTER4U Project Management Handbook and Risk Management Plan aims to unveil the management structure upon which the projects will operate. BETTER4U is a multidisciplinary project involving multiple partners of diverse expertise from various scientific fields. The nodes and activities of BETTER4U are designed in such a way as to promote the existence of effective procedures and proactive measures ensuring the smooth function of its governance bodies and activities.

2. Project Governance Structure

The organizational structure of the project consists of the following Governance Bodies: i) the General Assembly (GA), as the main governance body; ii) the Steering Committee (SC), as the body responsible for overseeing the smooth conduct of project activities, and; iii) the Dissemination Committee (DC), as the body responsible for the dissemination and communication of the project's results and findings. Two additional bodies are included, namely the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) and the Patient Advisory Board (PAB), as elaborated below.

2.1. Coordination and Management Team (CMT)

From the beginning of the project, a CMT will serve as the main body responsible to ensure the efficient and timely conduct of all BETTER4U activities, as well as the achievement of timely and maximum cohesion between administrative and scientific tasks. The CMT will be responsible for undertaking: i) the daily management of the project and the conduct of all relevant, daily administrative tasks; ii) the overall monitoring of the project's progress and obligation compliance among partners; iii) the creation, collection and review, as well as the timely and appropriate submission of all deliverables in cooperation with work package (WP) leaders and the project coordinator (CO); iv) the creation, collection and review of financial statements, certifications, and/or other specific requested documents to the Funding Authority, as well as the timely distribution of the budget deriving from the Granting Authority to the project beneficiaries ; v) the storage of all data, results and findings retrieved from all WPs, vi) the leading and monitoring the scientific and technical activities concerning implementation of the project; vii) the communications between consortium partners and/or between consortium partners and the general public or other scientific entities or stakeholders; viii) the organization and preparation of the project's governance bodies' meetings; ix) communication and reporting to the Granting Authority and European Commission, essentially acting as the link between them and the consortium. The composition of the CMT is described in **Table 1**. Integration of additional representatives of consortium partners can be continuous throughout the duration of the project.

Table 1. Members and functions of the BETTER4U Coordination and Management Team

Title	Person Responsible	Organization Abbreviation	Contact Details
Project Coordinator	George Dedoussis	HUA	dedousi@hua.gr Tel: +30 210 95 49 179 El. Venizelou 70, 17671, Athens, Greece
Project Manager	Maria Kafyra	HUA	mariakaf@hua.gr Tel: +30 210 95 49 212 El. Venizelou 70, 17671, Athens, Greece
Technical & Innovation Manager	Christos Diou	HUA	cdiou@hua.gr Tel: +30 210 95 49 449 El. Venizelou 70, 17671, Athens, Greece
Dissemination & Exploitation Manager	Stephan Kampshoff	EUFIC	stephan.kampshoff@eufic.org , Rue Belliard 2A (3rd Floor), 1040 Brussels, Belgium
Financial & Administrative Support Staff	Vasiliki Vavouraki	HUA	vvavouraki@hua.gr Tel: +30 697 88 86 129 El. Venizelou 70, 17671, Athens, Greece
Financial & Administrative Support Staff	Anna Maria Bavea	HUA	a.bavea@hua.gr , Tel: +30 697 21 64 002 El. Venizelou 70, 17671, Athens, Greece

2.2. General Assembly (GA)

From the onset until the conclusion of the BETTER4U activities, the GA will serve as the main regulatory body, chaired by the project coordinator (CO) and consisting of one representative for each consortium partner authorized to deliberate, negotiate and make decisions in all matters presented to the GA. Ordinary GA meetings will be held at least every 9 months throughout the duration of the project, with the coordinator notifying the members at least 45 calendar days prior and sending the agenda at least 3 weeks before the scheduled meeting. Regular GA meetings will refer to operational management issues unless stated otherwise in the meeting agenda. The GA can make decisions on all matters surrounding content, finances and intellectual property rights (i.e. proposals for amendments to the Grant Agreement for submission to the Granting Authority or modifications to the consortium plan or structure). All decision making and intra-team reporting (i.e. on activities, deliverables and internal reports) can and will be presented to the GA. All partners are invited to join those meetings.

All decisions requiring a voting will be sought to be achieved through consensus if possible, but if this is not feasible, a quorum of 2/3 of members will be needed for a valid decision. Each GA member shall have one vote. GA members have the right to exercise a veto in case

any legitimate interests of theirs would be severely affected by a certain decision of a Consortium Body. GA voting members are listed below in **Table 2**. In case of unforeseen absence in a GA meeting, a partner can inform the CO beforehand about their decision if they cannot attend. Associated Partner members are excluded from voting on and vetoing GA decisions regarding financial changes, budget distribution or excess payments and/or changes in the GA to be submitted to the Granting Authority.

Table 2. Voting members of the BETTER4U General Assembly (GA)

No	Organization	Organization Abbreviation	Member
1	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	George Dedoussis
2	CENTRO DE ESTUDOS E INVESTIGAÇÃO EM DINÂMICAS SOCIAIS E SAÚDE	CEIDSS	Ana Rito
3	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN NUTRITION HUMAINE RHONE-ALPES	CRNH-RA	Julie-Anne Nazarre (Anestis Dougkas as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
4	REGION HOVEDSTADEN	REGIONH	Klaus Bønnelykke
5	EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL	EUFIC	Stephan Kampshoff
6	DIETHNES PANEPISTIMIO ELLADOS	IHU	Maria Hassapidou (Ion Pagkalos as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
7	Karolinska Institutet	KI	Ioannis Ioakeimidis (Anna Ek as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
8	MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	MUW	Eva Schernhammer (Magda Zebrowska as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
9	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	UCY	Constantinos Deltas (Panayiota Veloudi as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
10	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	UH	Karri Silventoinen
11	UNIVERSIDAD DE NAVARRA	UNAV	Maira Bes Rastrollo
12	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGent	Nick Verhaeghe (Ruben Willems as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
13	UNIWERSYTET SWPS	SWPS	Aleksandra Łuszczżyńska (Paulina Krzywicka as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
14	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU	Anders Eriksson
15	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN	HMGU	Marie Standl (Elisabeth Thiering as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
16	STICHTING VU	VUA	Dorret I. Boomsma (Rene Pool as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
17	THE EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE STUDY OF OBESITY	EASO	Lisa Heggie

18	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	UNIVIE	Lisa Marie Breyer
19	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WIS	Eran Segal (David Krongauz as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
20	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES S.A.	WINGS	Vera Stavroulaki
21	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI CAGLIARI	UNICA	Vasilios Fanos
22	BIOCLINICA SA	BIOCLINICA SA	Cristinel Gheorghiu
23	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos
24	TAMPERE UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL AND TAMPERE UNIVERSITY	TAUH	Terho Lehtimaki
25	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mouggiakakou
26	QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute	QIMR	Nick Martin
27	BRADFORD TEACHING HOSPITALS NHS FOUNDATION TRUST	BiB	Gillian Santorelli
28	QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	QMUL	Eirini Marouli

2.3. Steering Committee (SC)

Supporting the work of the GA, the SC will serve as the main supervisory body for monitoring the effective and efficient activities of the project throughout its entirety, chaired by the CO (unless otherwise decided by a majority of at least two thirds) and consisting of all work package (WP) leaders. Ordinary SC meetings will be held at least every 2 months throughout the duration of the project, with the coordinator notifying the members at least 2 weeks prior and sending the agenda at least 1 week before the scheduled meeting. Regarding decision-making processes, SC shall seek a consensus among its members.

Regular SC meetings will refer to execution and implementation matters unless stated otherwise in the meeting agenda. The SC can and will support the CO in: i) monitoring project progress by providing guidance and ensuring the timely preparation and submission of project deliverables, data and/or any material related to meeting with the Granting Authority, ii) agreeing on specific actions to ensure the successful conduct and cohesion among project’s inter- and intra- WP activities; iii) monitoring the quality of work produced within the nodes of the different WP; iii) discussing and advising the CO on legal matters and; ii) preparing and bringing relevant content of joint publications in the attention of the GA and the Dissemination Committee (DC). SC members are listed below in **Table 3**. In case of unforeseen

absence in a SC meeting, a partner can inform the CO beforehand about their decision if they cannot attend.

Table 3. Members of the BETTER4U Steering Committee (SC)

WP	WP Leader	Organization Abbreviation	Member
WP1	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	George Dedoussis
WP2	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	UNIVIE	Lisa Marie Breyer
WP3	UNIWERSYTET SWPS	SWPS	Aleksandra Łuszczynska
WP4	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU	Anders Eriksson
WP5	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mougiakakou
WP6	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos
WP7	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	Yannis Manios
WP8	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGent	Nick Verhaeghe (Ruben Willems as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
WP9	EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL	EUFIC	Stephan Kampshoff

2.4. Dissemination Committee (DC)

Regarding dissemination and communication of the project, the DC will serve as the main supervisory body responsible for the proper and timely dissemination of project results and findings. The DC will be chaired by the CO and consisting of all work package (WP) leaders, along with one designated member from each consortium partner. Ordinary DC meetings will be held at least every 9 months throughout the duration of the project, with the coordinator notifying the members at least 2 weeks prior and sending the agenda at least 1 week before the scheduled meeting. Regarding decision-making processes, DC shall seek a consensus among its members.

Regular DC meetings will refer to the communication of the project’s outcomes to the general public, scientific community and relevant stakeholders. The DC can and will: i) coordinate and monitor the dissemination of the project’s results by bringing dissemination plan and suggestions to the attention of the GA; ii) organizing symposia, workshops and preparing press releases relevant to the existing data, and; iii) support the CO in preparing GA meetings. DC members are listed below in **Table 4**. In case of unforeseen absence in a DC meeting, a partner can inform the CO beforehand about their decision if they cannot attend.

Table 4. Members of the BETTER4U Dissemination Committee (DC)

No	Organization	Organization Abbreviation	Member
1	CHAROKOPIO PANEPISTIMIO	HUA	George Dedoussis
2	CENTRO DE ESTUDOS E INVESTIGAÇÃO EM DINÂMICAS SOCIAIS E SAÚDE	CEIDSS	Ana Rito
3	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN NUTRITION HUMAINE RHONE-ALPES	CRNH-RA	Julie-Anne Nazarre (Anestis Dougkas as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
4	REGION HOVEDSTADEN	REGIONH	Klaus Bønnelykke
5	EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL	EUFIC	Stephan Kampshoff
6	DIETHNES PANEPISTIMIO ELLADOS	IHU	Maria Hassapidou (Ion Pagkalos as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
7	Karolinska Institutet	KI	Ioannis Ioakeimidis (Anna Ek as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
8	MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	MUW	Eva Schernhammer (Magda Zebrowska as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
9	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	UCY	Constantinos Deltas (Panayiota Veloudi as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
10	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	UH	Karri Silventoinen
11	UNIVERSIDAD DE NAVARRA	UNAV	Maira Bes Rastrollo
12	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGent	Nick Verhaeghe (Ruben Willems as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
13	UNIWERSYTET SWPS	SWPS	Aleksandra Łuszczzyńska (Paulina Krzywicka as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
14	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU	Anders Eriksson
15	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN	HMGU	Elisabeth Thiering
16	STICHTING VU	VUA	Dorret I. Boomsma (Rene Pool as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
17	THE EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE STUDY OF OBESITY	EASO	Lisa Heggie
18	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	UNIVIE	Rodessa May Marquez
19	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WIS	Eran Segal (David Krongauz as an <i>Alternate Member</i>)
20	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES S.A.	WINGS	Vera Stavroulaki

21	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI CAGLIARI	UNICA	Vasilios Fanos
22	BIOCLINICA SA	BIOCLINICA SA	Cristinel Gheorghiu
23	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Anastasios Delopoulos
24	TAMPERE UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL AND TAMPERE UNIVERSITY	TAUH	Nina Mononen
25	UNIVERSITAET BERN	UBern	Stavroula Mougiakakou
26	QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute	QIMR	Nick Martin
27	BRADFORD TEACHING HOSPITALS NHS FOUNDATION TRUST	BiB	Gillian Santorelli
28	QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	QMUL	Eirini Marouli

2.5. External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)

In an effort to maximize the efficiency of all project’s proceedings, an External Expert Advisory Group (EEAB) has been appointed to advise on matters surrounding the project, for example potential ethics and technical risk identification and management. The EEAB is a governance body of experts external to the project providing the consortium with independent evaluation to the project work plan, as well as valuable guidance and recommendations on scientific, technical and ethical/legal matters and procedures. The CO is responsible to bring all matters discussed in the context of the EEAB to the attention of the GA. Members of the EEAB will meet with the CO (HUA) whenever necessary and discuss matters relevant to the project. The content and meetings of these interactions will be then transferred to the project’s General Assembly (GA) by the CO. Members of the EEAB will sign one Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) with the coordinator, who is authorized to sign on behalf of all the consortium partners, except for Karolinska Institutet (KI), and a second NDA with KI (*appointment of the members has been completed and the preparations for signature of the NDAs is currently pending/ongoing*). EEAB members shall be allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights.

The BETTER4U EEAB members are:

- Frank Hu, Chair of Department of Nutrition, Fredrick J. Stare Professor of Nutrition and Epidemiology, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health and Professor of Medicine, Harvard Medical School and Brigham and Women’s Hospital.
- José Ordovas, Professor of Nutrition and Genetics, Gerald J. and Dorothy R. Friedman School of Nutrition Science and Policy.
- Vagelis Papakonstantinou, Professor on Personal Data Protection Law, Faculty of Law & Criminology, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Attorney At Law, MPllegal

- Fariba Ahmadizar, Assistant Professor, Molecular (Pharmaco)Epidemiology, Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary Care, Department Data Science & Biostatistics, Global Health, University Medical Center Utrecht
- Sophie Siest, President of the Santorini Conferences (SCs) Association

2.6. Patient Advisory Board

Regarding the conduct of the randomized clinical trial (RCT) within the nodes of the BETTER4ALL Lifestyle Intervention, a Patient Advisory Board (PAB) will be established to further enable continuous feedback from intervention volunteers. More specifically, RCT participants of each clinical site will be randomly selected at the beginning of the trial to provide monthly feedback on their views of the intervention proceedings. Feedback regarding intervention implementation, such as the use of the proposed monitoring tools or the feasibility of adoption of the proposed recommendations will allow for the identification of barriers and facilitators and the timely integration of proposed measures to increase intervention adherence and efficacy.

3. Risk Management Plan

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of the BETTER4U Project and the need for the efficient and simultaneous completion of multiple tasks, a strict risk management plan has been set out to carry out continuous evaluation, minimize potential risk consequences and increase the availability and urgency effective mitigation measures. In cooperation with WINGS [as the relevant Task Leader of *Task 1.3 Quality and Risk Management (M1-M48)*], the CO will provide a centralized risk management strategy and remain in constant communication with all WP leaders and consortium partners to ensure the quality of the work produced within the project nodes. For this purpose, the CO will: i) define and promote the use of templates for documentation, presentations and communication policies, ii) install or ensure the existence of the necessary mechanisms for the identification, communication and mitigation of potential; iii) monitor the achievements produced according to the proposed Key Performance Indicators (as outlined in the Description of Action-DoA), and; iv) promote cost-effective mitigation measures to minimize the spending of resources towards mitigation actions. This collaborative effort will allow for the anticipation of potential risk and proactively complete the existence of mitigation measures prior to their potential appearance.

In this context, the following STEPwise approach will be adopted, according to the stages outlined below:

i. Risk Analysis and Evaluation Process

The risk planning outlined in this first step takes place from the beginning of the project, where prediction and identification of risk management procedures and responsibilities is maximized. The cornerstone of the analysis and evaluation process is set in the risks already

outlined within the project’s DoA, as also presented here in **Table 5**. Complementary to these, an additional, continuous process of risk identification will be taking place throughout the project. The latter will concern the spotting of new risks associated with project activities as they unfold or are beginning to unfold. In the case of a novel risk appearing, the CO and SC will be notified upon identification. Risk analysis will subsequently assess the probability and severity of each potential risk and attempt to estimate and minimize its impact to the relevant project task(s) or to the project as a whole.

ii. Development of mitigation measures

Each new risk can be either urgent, upcoming or complete. Mitigation measures for each risk will be subsequently, immediately identified by the CO and the relevant Task Leader and outlined in a detailed mitigation proposal. One person from a specific partner will be assigned to complete the risk mitigation process, in cooperation with the CO. Mitigation measures for risks already identified within the DoA are outline in **Table 5**.

iii. Review schedule, process and responsible parties

During the application of each mitigation measure, a schedule for regular reviews by the CO and the relevant Task Leader will be outlined, aiming to assess measure accuracy and maximize impact. Responsible parties can and should bring all proposals and measures undertaken to the attention of the SC, which can, in turn, evaluate the process and bring any urgent matters to the attention of the GA.

Table 5. List of BETTER4U Critical Risks as included in the DoA.

Risk Number	Risk Type	Description	Likelihood	Severity	WPs	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Management	Conflict among partners	Low	Medium	WP3, WP6, WP2, WP8, WP5, WP9, WP1, WP7, WP4	Regular meeting described in management structure will ensure revision of the conflicts
2	Management	Delay in meeting the deadlines	Medium	Medium	WP3, WP6, WP2, WP8, WP5, WP9, WP1, WP7, WP4	Project manager and involved WP/task leaders take a closer look at the subsequent tasks they impact. Plans will be analysed and modified to achieve the project needs even under delays
3	Management	Lack of specification detail and understanding of user requirements.	Medium	Medium	WP3, WP6, WP2, WP8, WP5, WP9, WP1, WP7, WP4	Regular Consortium & WP meetings to ensure alignment.
4	Technical	Access to data not granted by ethical committees	Low	High	WP2	Several data providers have been selected to mitigate this risk. Alternative data sources will be envisaged or reducing access to research partners
5		Individual conditions not			WP3	A first mitigation measure was taken by choosing highly prevalent conditions

	Technical	well represented in datasets.	Medium	High		from literature. Second mitigation option is to analyze the datasets to identify alternative highly prevalent conditions.
6	Technical	Lack of interpretability and explainability of the SCMs.	Low	Medium	WP5	Visualization of the models' inputs, outputs and their associations; interfaces that allow HCPs to interact with the model; and regular Consortium & WP meetings will ensure that BETTER4U members and HCPs have a better understanding of the models' predictions.
7	Technical	Difficulties in the implementation of the federated learning infrastructure.	Medium	Medium	WP5	NVIDIA has already expressed its willingness to support BETTER4U. A responsible person will take care of the coordination and integration of the federated learning approach at each site, to ensure smooth collaboration
8	Technical	Complexity due to scalability to big data.	Medium	High	WP5	The involved teams have experience and track record is successfully in dealing with moderate to big sized data sets. The WP leader has experience in dealing with big data coming from people with diabetes and the development of software to deal with them.
9	Technical	Poor generalisation of the AI methods due to e.g., overfitting	Medium	High	WP5	Systematic investigation of data diversity and biases, use of cross-validation approaches, pretraining and transfer learning approaches
10	Technical	Difficulties in patient enrolment and engagement in the intervention study	Medium	High	WP7	Promotion of project via reaching-out to professional associations and local stakeholders and extensive social media campaigns. A number of participants will additionally be recruited to have enough backup in case this is needed. Continuous monitoring of participants for recognition and tackling of barriers.
11	Technical	Missing input to run the cost effectiveness analysis.	Low	Medium	WP8	Mitigation strategy is to use historical data to complement missing data.
12	Technical	Costs and workload exceed the amounts estimated in the proposal	Low	High	WP3, WP6, WP2, WP8, WP5, WP9, WP1, WP7, WP4	Ensure that all partners are committed to performing the work within the cost estimates in the proposal and that each partner understands that they will have to bear the risk of funding shortfalls or workload exceedances.

13	Technical	Lack of visibility of project achievements	Medium	Medium	WP9	The effectiveness of dissemination activities will be constantly monitored and additional channels of dissemination will be utilised if necessary.
14	Technical	Low stakeholder engagement and interaction in the Sustainable Food System Network	Medium	Medium	WP9	Keep channel interesting based on stakeholder interests, provide support, workshops.

4. Conclusion

The outlined governance structure and risk management approaches aim to maximize the successful conduct of all BETTER4U proposed activities. All governance bodies, the project CO and all partners will collaborate closely and effectively to ensure the quality and timely production of the proposed project proceedings.

5. Contact and details

Coordinator, Project manager and Work Package 1 leader

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